

Effectiveness of Video Simulation in Enhancing Medical Students' Confidence and Knowledge in Conducting Joint Examinations

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Abstract

Background: Developing clinical skills in undergraduate medical students requires significant effort to meet the required standards. Educational research assessing how different teaching interventions affect medical students' perceptions of self-confidence and knowledge in performing joint examinations is essential. This study evaluated the impact of integrating video simulation into skills training on students' knowledge and confidence in orthopaedic clinical examination.

Aim: To assess the effectiveness of video simulation in enhancing third-year medical students' confidence and knowledge in conducting orthopaedic examinations.

Methods: This pre–post intervention study was conducted on 54 Nottingham University Medical Students at Nottingham University Hospitals NHS Trust using videos created by the Clinical Teaching Fellows in Trauma and Orthopaedics.

Results: On average, students' confidence levels increased by approximately 41% when comparing their pre- and post-training surveys. Many transitioned from uncertainty to greater confidence on the Likert scale regarding their ability to perform joint examinations. However, a small subset exhibited decreased confidence post-training, suggesting moving from 'unknown unknowns' to 'known unknowns' reduces confidence. Interim surveys revealed that, while pre-training confidence varied significantly, students have opted for neutral responses, indicating uncertainty. Post-training, nearly all students reported clearer self-assessment, either expressing confidence in conducting examinations or recognizing their knowledge limitations.

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Conclusion: This study shows that combining video examination with hands-on, peer-led teaching significantly improves medical students' confidence and understanding of musculoskeletal joint examinations. While videos alone helped to some extent, the biggest gains were seen when students also had the chance to practice and receive instant feedback in person.

Keywords: *video, physical examination, clinical skills, teaching, medical student.*

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Introduction

Physical examination is a crucial skill for medical students and doctors to determine diagnosis, improve patient care, and prevent unnecessary tests (Garibaldi & Elder, 2021). It remains an essential daily clinical skill. Musculoskeletal (MSK) issues are among the most common reasons for visits to primary care, making up 21.1% of attendances (Keavy et al., 2022). Despite this, it accounts for less than 2% of teaching time in medical schools overall, with significant variation between institutions (Flatt et al., 2023).

Teaching MSK examinations in medical school has been separated into specific joint examinations, for example shoulder examination and knee examinations (Moßhammer et al., 2017). The effectiveness of an efficient and thorough examination allows the student/doctor to create an accurate differential diagnosis and help guide further investigation and management.⁴ Due to our increased reliance on radiological investigations, the art of physical examination appears to be disappearing (Feddock, 2007). Therefore, it is important to innovate and design new methods of teaching in order for students to understand the concepts and relevance of clinical examinations (Feddock, 2007).

Traditionally, physical examination has been taught in face-to-face small group sessions. The importance of novice learners interacting with the expert learner, enhances the students' experience through situated learning (Lave & Wenger, 1991). Whilst research has shown that face-to-face teaching appears to be superior, technology is evolving (Brewer et al., 2021).

Technology has become an important aspect of medical education over the last 25 years and as technology advances, so should our teaching methods. This became an acute necessity during the COVID-19 pandemic, where face-to-face education disappeared and other methods of teaching were rapidly employed (Almarzooq et al., 2020). The pandemic led to a surge in online medical resources and therefore technology has become a key part of medical education (Flatt et al., 2023). It allows several advantages including accessibility and availability (Brewer et al., 2021). However, transferring a face-to-face teaching session into an online format does not

necessarily create high quality learning (Brewer et al., 2021). The surge in video presentations and online resources if peer reviewed and accurate can be useful, but it is important to note that misinformation can be just as easily spread, especially with open access platforms (Urch et al., 2016). The high volume of poor quality and incorrect content dilutes access to high quality content (Zwerus et al., 2021).

A recent randomised controlled trial showed that the use of customised educational video resources significantly improves the teaching of clinical skills when used as an adjunct to face-to-face methods of teaching but not as a replacement (Flatt et al., 2023). This is further highlighted by a study where students participated in an online video-based learning module alongside bedside teaching and mentioned that the module could not replace hands-on teaching (Alomar, 2022). Other studies which compared video-based learning with hands-on teaching showed that due to lack of feedback in the video-based learning environment, students performed poorly when compared to their face-to-face counterparts (Backstein et al., 2004). Students also preferred one-to-one hands-on teaching compared to just an online video when learning physical examination (Smith et al., 2012).

Going beyond videos research is currently ongoing in virtual reality models as a potential teaching modality for undergraduates and postgraduate students (Cheung et al., 2023; Lohre et al., 2020; Mao et al., 2021; Schöbel et al., 2024). However, further evaluation is required to see if this would be an effective tool and improve clinical competence (Cheung et al., 2023).

Methods

This pre–post intervention study assessed the effectiveness of video simulation in enhancing third year medical students’ confidence and knowledge in conducting orthopaedic examinations. It was conducted on 54 students.

At Nottingham University Hospitals NHS Trust, the Clinical Teaching Fellows in Trauma and Orthopaedics deliver teaching sessions on Musculoskeletal Diseases and Disorders to undergraduate medical students at Nottingham University School of Medicine (SoM).

In collaboration with the Nottingham University SoM, they developed and recorded a series of joint examination videos using simulated patients. These videos serve as a learning resource for joint examination techniques and are accessible to medical students at the Nottingham University SoM.

At the Nottingham University SoM, medical students entering their clinical years begin with the 'Foundations for Practice' (FFP) clinical phase, which includes rotations in Medicine, Surgery, Obstetrics and Gynaecology, and various other specialties. During the six-week Surgery rotation, one week is dedicated to the topic of joint pain. As part of this, students participate in a Mini-CEX (Clinical Evaluation Exercise) session, where they receive instruction on hip and knee examinations and are given the opportunity to practice these skills on their peers.

A seven-item questionnaire was developed to assess students’ confidence and knowledge regarding joint examinations. Two items measured students’ self-perceived knowledge and skills in performing joint examinations, while another two assessed their confidence in anatomical understanding of the hip and knee. These four questions used a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (strongly agree) to 5 (strongly

disagree). The remaining three items evaluated detailed knowledge appropriate to the students' level of training, using a multiple-choice format with a single best answer selected from five options.

This questionnaire was reviewed by two research experts, who provided feedback to refine and optimise its content and utility.

The training constituted both video simulation and a face-to-face skills lab teaching session including both a lecture and peer to peer practice. The questionnaire was administered to students at three points: before the start of training, after watching the video, and following the skills lab session (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Diagram describing the study's timeline

The questionnaire was distributed at three stages: before training (pre-intervention), after watching the video simulation, and following the practical skills lab session.

Results

This study is conducted on 54 3rd year medical students over 9 weeks. 35 of them completed the pre-training questionnaire, 30 of them completed the interim questionnaire, and 38 have completed the last questionnaire. A total of 103 responses were analysed across three time points: pre-training, post-video, and post-video plus hands-on teaching.

Students reported a marked increase in confidence regarding their knowledge in joint examinations (Figure 2). Pre-training, only 34.3% of students felt confident in their knowledge (agree or strongly agree).

Figure 2. Students' Confidence about the Knowledge Required for Joint Examinations

Following the video intervention alone, neutral responses dominated (53.3%), indicating persisting uncertainty. However, after the complete training (video simulation and teaching), 68.4% of students reported higher confidence in their knowledge in joint examinations, with “strongly agree” responses rising notably from 2.9% to 34.2%. This change in student responses is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

Similarly, students’ confidence in examination skills and approach increased from 31.4% in the pre-training assessment to 68.4% in the post-training assessment (Figure 3), with a clear shift from neutral or negative responses to positive ones. This improvement is also statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

Figure 3. Students' Confidence about the Skills and Approach Required for Joint Examinations

Confidence in anatomical knowledge of joint examinations also improved. For the knee examination, only 31.5% of students felt confident (agree or strongly agree) in their anatomical knowledge of knee examination in the pre-training assessment. This proportion has increased to 68.4% after the full training, which is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

A similar pattern was observed for the hip examination, where agreement rose from 28.6% in the pre-training assessment to 60.5% (Agree plus Strongly Agree) in the post-training assessment (Agree plus Strongly Agree), with a statistically significant p-value of 0.007.

Figure 4 shows that the proportion of students correctly identifying which ligaments are assessed by Varus and Valgus stress tests has increased from 51.4% in the pre-training assessment to 94.7% in the post-training assessment. This finding reflects a statistically significant increase in their knowledge regarding knee examination ($p = 0.014$).

Similarly, students’ recognition of the correct interpretation of a positive Thomas test rose significantly from 48.6% in the pre-training assessment to 94.7% in the post-training assessment (Figure 5) ($p = 0.001$).

Figure 4. What do Varus and Valgus Stress Tests Assess?

Figure 5. What does a Positive Thomas Test indicate?

When asked about appropriate steps to supplement a joint examination, most students selected the correct answer (All the above) even prior to training (82.9%), which further increased to 97.4% in post-training assessment. This improvement, however, was not statistically significant ($p = 0.098$).

Discussion

This study assessed the effectiveness of video simulation in enhancing third-year medical students' confidence and knowledge in conducting orthopaedic examination of the hip and knee.

Although video simulations are a consistent way to present clinical education, they were not sufficient on their own. After watching the videos, many students still felt uncertain about their knowledge and clinical skills. Post video but pre-practical teaching, 53.3% of students reported neutral confidence levels regarding their joint examination knowledge (Figure 2), and 53.3% also felt unsure about their examination skills and approach (Figure 3). This suggests that while videos may provide foundational content, they simply do not replace the core value of in-person, interactive teaching.

In fact, some students reported feeling less confident after the videos. For example, confidence in anatomical knowledge of the knee fell from 31.5% (Strongly Agree + Agree) pre-training to just 20% post-video. This could possibly suggest a "conscious incompetence" stage of learning—where students become more aware of what they do not know (von Hoyer et al., 2022). This is actually an important step in skill development but highlights the need for further guidance after initial video exposure.

Once students participated in structured peer-led practice following the videos, their confidence improved significantly across all the areas that were measured. This included general knowledge, anatomical understanding, and clinical application. These gains were not just broad but specific, showing that combining visual learning with active practice can help solidify clinical education.

This improvement supports the idea that clinical skills are best learned through peer led practice. Furthermore, hands-on teaching allows for immediate critical feedback and correction. These findings are consistent with the concept of situated learning, where learners gain improved knowledge through live in-person practice whilst supported by more experienced peers (Lave & Wenger, 1991). What this research does not answer is the question of whether the use of a video as pre-learning further enhances learning in face-to-face sessions. This would be an important question to answer in future research.

The most consistent outcome across all domains was an increase in confidence. Before the training, many students reported feeling unsure or neutral. Confidence in joint examination knowledge increased from 34.3% pre-training to 68.4% post-training ($p < 0.001$), and confidence in examination skills similarly rose from 31.4% to 68.4% ($p < 0.001$). This demonstrates that the practical, feedback-rich teaching environment used in this study helped develop students from uncertainty to self-assuredness. That said, confidence does not necessarily equate to competence. Therefore, potential future studies could examine whether these self-reported confidence gains translate into actual clinical competency.

Overall, the data show that the use of video simulation followed by structured peer-led practice significantly enhances both confidence and clinical understanding in MSK examination skills among medical students.

Videos have a role in medical education. They are scalable, consistent, and very accessible (Youssef et al., 2022). Students still require the opportunity to apply what they observe, ask questions, and gain feedback on the spot. The risk of teaching by videos alone, in addition to a lower level of attained learning and confidence, is that

open-access or low-quality videos may lead to incorrect or incomplete knowledge (Urch et al., 2016).

The number of students who correctly identified the ligaments assessed by Varus and Valgus stress tests increased from 51.4% to 94.7% after full training. Similarly, the correct identification of the implication of a positive Thomas test improved from 48.6% to 94.7%. This could reflect on how active learning, especially when students have the opportunity to physically perform special tests in front of mentors and peers thus, receive constructive feedback can enhance understanding and improve retention in ways video solely cannot.

An interesting finding was the students' responses to the multiple-choice question (MCQ) that included "All of the above" as an option. Before any intervention, 82.9% of students correctly selected "All of the above," and this increased to 97.4% after the full training. Using this type of option in MCQs can serve as a 'default' guess during uncertainty. It may suggest a lack of clarity in the question itself (Naidoo, 2023). Best practice encourages the use of well-reasoned options that test a student's ability to apply knowledge rather than rely on process-of-elimination strategies (Gottlieb et al., 2023). This observation may highlight the need for not just improved teaching methods, but also a more thought-out assessment design.

Conclusion

This study shows that combining video examination with hands-on, peer-led teaching significantly improves medical students' confidence and understanding of MSK joint examinations. While videos alone helped to some extent, the biggest gains were seen when students also had the chance to practice and receive instant feedback in person.

Recommendation

Future studies could look at whether improvements in students' confidence and skills are maintained over time and whether they lead to better performance in OSCE exams or real-life clinical practice and whether teaching without the use of videos pre learning results is the same level of attainment. It would also be valuable to test this combined learning approach (video simulation plus peer-led teaching) in other settings and with larger cohorts participating.

Limitations

The study involved a relatively small group of third-year students from a single medical school. Therefore, results may not be generalizable to various other school settings. Unfortunately, not all students completed each section of the questionnaire, which could potentially distort results as a form of response bias.

Practice Points

- Video simulation improves medical students' confidence in MSK joint examinations.
- Confidence gains are most significant when videos are combined with hands-on teaching.
- Video alone may increase awareness of knowledge gaps but not resolve them.
- Peer-led teaching with feedback enhances learning effectiveness.

- Further research is needed to isolate the impact of hands-on teaching on confidence and knowledge.

Declaration of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Author Contributions

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References

Almarzooq, Z., Lopes, M., & Kochar, A. (2020). Virtual learning during the COVID-19 pandemic: A disruptive technology in graduate medical education. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*, 75(20). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacc.2020.04.015>

Alomar, A. Z. (2022). Undergraduate medical students' perceptions of an online audio-visual-based module for teaching musculoskeletal physical examination skills. *Journal of Medical Education and Curricular Development*, 9, 23821205221078794. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23821205221078794>

Backstein, D., Agnidis, Z., Regehr, G., & Reznick, R. (2004). The effectiveness of video feedback in the acquisition of orthopedic technical skills. *The American Journal of Surgery*, 187(3), 427–432. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjsurg.2003.12.011>

Brewer, P. E., Racy, M., Hampton, M., Mushtaq, F., Tomlinson, J. E., & Ali, F. M. (2021). A three-arm single blind randomised control trial of naïve medical students performing a shoulder joint clinical examination. *BMC Medical Education*, 21(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-021-02822-5>

Cheung, V. Y. T., Tang, Y. M., & Chan, K. K. L. (2023). Medical students' perception of the application of a virtual reality training model to acquire vaginal examination

- skills. *International Journal of Gynecology & Obstetrics*, 161(3), 827–832. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijgo.14670>
- Feddock, C. A. (2007). The lost art of clinical skills. *The American Journal of Medicine*, 120(4), 374–378. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjmed.2007.01.023>
- Flatt, E., Brewer, P., Racy, M., Mushtaq, F., Ashworth, R., Ali, F., & Tomlinson, J. (2023). Can educational video resources improve learning when used to augment traditional teaching of clinical examination? A randomized controlled trial of novice medical students. *BMC Medical Education*, 23(1), 21. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-022-03974-8>
- Garibaldi, B. T., & Elder, A. (2021). Seven reasons why the physical examination remains important. *Journal of the Royal College of Physicians of Edinburgh*, 51(3), 211–214. <https://doi.org/10.4997/jrcpe.2021.301>
- Gottlieb, M., Bailitz, J., Fix, M., Shappell, E., & Wagner, M. J. (2023). Educator's blueprint: A how-to guide for developing high-quality multiple choice questions. *AEM Education and Training*, 7(1), e10836. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aet2.10836>
- Keavy, R., Horton, R., & Al-Dadah, O. (2022). The prevalence of musculoskeletal presentations in general practice: An epidemiological study. *Family Practice*, 40(1). <https://doi.org/10.1093/fampra/cmab055>
- Lave, J., & Wenger, E. (1991). *Situated learning: Legitimate peripheral participation*. Cambridge University Press.
- Lohre, R., Bois, A. J., Athwal, G. S., & Goel, D. P. (2020). Improved complex skill acquisition by immersive virtual reality training. *The Journal of Bone and Joint Surgery. American Volume*, 102(6), e26. <https://doi.org/10.2106/JBJS.19.00982>
- Mao, R. Q., Lan, L., Kay, J., Lohre, R., Ayeni, O. R., Goel, D. P., & de Sa, D. (2021). Immersive virtual reality for surgical training: A systematic review. *Journal of Surgical Research*, 268, 40–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2021.06.045>
- Moßhammer, D., Graf, J., Joos, S., & Hertkorn, R. (2017). Physical examination in undergraduate medical education in the field of general practice: A scoping review. *BMC Medical Education*, 17(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-017-1074-1>
- Naidoo, M. (2023). The pearls and pitfalls of setting high quality multiple choice questions for clinical medicine. *South African Family Practice*, 65(1), e1–e4. <https://doi.org/10.4102/safp.v65i1.5726>
- Schöbel, T., Schuschke, L., Youssef, Y., Rotzoll, D., Theopold, J., & Osterhoff, G. (2024). Immersive virtuelle Realität in der Orthopädie und Unfallchirurgie als Wahlfach für Medizinstudierende. *Orthopädie*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00132-024-04491-w>
- Smith, W., Rafeek, R., Marchan, S., & Paryag, A. (2012). The use of video-clips as a teaching aide. *European Journal of Dental Education*, 16(2), 91–96. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0579.2011.00724.x>
- Urch, E., Taylor, S. A., Cody, E., Fabricant, P. D., Burket, J. C., O'Brien, S. J., Dines, D. M., & Dines, J. S. (2016). The quality of open-access video-based orthopaedic instructional content for the shoulder physical exam is inconsistent. *HSS Journal*, 12(3), 209–215. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11420-016-9508-6>

von Hoyer, J. F., Bientzle, M., Cress, U., Grosser, J., Kimmerle, J., & Holtz, P. (2022). False certainty in the acquisition of anatomical and physiotherapeutic knowledge. *BMC Medical Education*, 22(1), 765. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-022-03820-x>

Youssef, S. C., Aydin, A., Canning, A., et al. (2022). Learning surgical skills through video-based education: A systematic review. *Surgical Innovation*, 30(2), 220–238. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15533506221120146>

Zwerus, E. L., Molenaars, R. J., Marijnissen, P. J., & Eygendaal, D. (2021). Accuracy and quality of educational videos for elbow physical examination: A search from the earliest year until October 2018. *Archives of Bone and Joint Surgery*, 9(1), 93–101. <https://doi.org/10.22038/abjs.2020.47221.2310>

Appendix

Table 1. Students' Confidence about the Knowledge Required for Joint Examinations

		Strongly Agree	Agree	Unsure	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Pre-Training	Count	1	11	8	9	6	35
	% within response	2.9%	31.4%	22.9%	25.7%	17.1%	100.0%
Post Video	Count	0	5	16	7	2	30
	% within response	0.0%	16.7%	53.3%	23.3%	6.7%	100.0%
Post Video & Teaching	Count	26	13	0	5	7	38
	% within response	34.2%	34.2%	0.0%	13.2%	18.4%	100.0%
Total	Count	14	29	24	21	15	103
	% within response	13.6%	28.2%	23.3%	20.4%	14.6%	100.0%

Note: *Statistically significant $p < 0.001$

Table 2. Students' Confidence about the Skills and Approach in Joint Examinations

		Strongly Agree	Agree	Not Decide	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Pre-Training	Count	2	9	9	9	6	35
	% within response	5.7%	25.7%	25.7%	25.7%	17.1%	100.0%
Post Video	Count	0	4	16	9	1	30
	% within response	0.0%	13.3%	53.3%	30.0%	3.3%	100.0%
Post Video & Teaching	Count	16	10	0	7	5	38
	% within response	42.1%	26.3%	0.0%	18.4%	13.2%	100.0%
Total	Count	18	23	25	25	12	103
	% within response	17.5%	22.3%	24.3%	24.3%	11.7%	100.0%

Note: *Statistically significant $p < 0.001$

Table 3. Students' Confidence about the Anatomical Knowledge of Knee Examination

		Strongly Agree	Agree	Not Decide	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Pre-Training	Count	3	8	12	10	2	35
	% within response	8.6%	22.9%	34.3%	28.6%	5.7%	100.0%
Post Video	Count	0	6	14	8	2	30
	% within response	0.0%	20.0%	46.7%	26.7%	6.7%	100.0%
Post Video & Teaching	Count	13	13	2	2	8	38
	% within response	34.2%	34.2%	5.3%	5.3%	21.1%	100.0%
Total	Count	16	27	28	20	12	103
	% within response	15.5%	26.2%	27.2%	19.4%	11.7%	100.0%

Note: *Statistically significant $p < 0.001$

Table 4. Students' Confidence about the Anatomical Knowledge of Hip Examination

		Strongly Agree	Agree	Not Decide	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Pre-Training	Count	3	7	9	15	1	35
	% within response	8.6%	20.0%	25.7%	42.9%	2.9%	100.0%
Post Video	Count	1	7	10	9	3	30
	% within response	3.3%	23.3%	33.3%	30.0%	10.0%	100.0%
Post Video & Teaching	Count	12	11	3	8	4	38
	% within response	31.6%	28.9%	7.9%	21.1%	10.5%	100.0%
Total	Count	16	25	22	32	8	103
	% within response	15.5%	24.3%	21.4%	31.1%	7.8%	100.0%

Note: *Statistically significant $p = 0.007$

Table 5. Knowledge of what do Varus and Valgus Stress Tests Assess

		Anterior Cruciate and Posterior Cruciate Ligaments	Medial Collateral and Lateral Collateral Ligaments	Medial Meniscus and Lateral Meniscus	Not sure	Stress Fractures	Total
Pre-Training	Count	3	18	3	10	1	35
	% within response	8.6%	51.4%	8.6%	28.6%	2.9%	100.0%
Post Video	Count	3	18	2	6	1	30
	% within response	10.0%	60.0%	6.7%	20.0%	3.3%	100.0%
Post Video & Teaching	Count	0	36	1	1	0	38
	% within response	0.0%	94.7%	2.6%	2.6%	0.0%	100.0%
Total	Count	6	72	6	17	2	103
	% within response	5.8%	69.9%	5.8%	16.5%	1.9%	100.0%

Note: *Statistically significant $p=0.014$

Table 6. Knowledge of what a Positive Thomas Test Indicates

		Hip Fixed Flexion Deformity	Joint Effusion	Not sure	Trochanteric Bursitis	Total
1 Pre-Training	Count	17	2	15	1	35
	% within response	48.6%	5.7%	42.9%	2.9%	100.0%
2 Post Video	Count	17	2	10	1	30
	% within response	56.7%	6.7%	33.3%	3.3%	100.0%
3 Post Video & Teaching	Count	36	0	1	1	38
	% within response	94.7%	0.0%	2.6%	2.6%	100.0%
Total	Count	70	4	26	3	103
	% within response	68.0%	3.9%	25.2%	2.9%	100.0%

Note: *Statistically significant $p=0.001$

Table 7. At the End of a Joint Examination, Knowledge of what else Can be Done to the Examination

		All the Above	Examine the Joint Above and Below	Not sure	Request X-Ray of the Joint	Total
Pre-Training	Count	29	5	0	1	35
	% within response	82.9%	14.3%	0.0%	2.9%	100.0%
Post Video	Count	23	3	1	3	30
	% within response	76.7%	10.0%	3.3%	10.0%	100.0%
Post Video & Teaching	Count	37	1	0	0	38
	% within response	97.4%	2.6%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%
Total	Count	89	9	1	4	103
	% within response	86.4%	8.7%	1.0%	3.9%	100.0%

Note: *Statistically not significant $p=0.098$

